

ISSUES OF FORMATION THE MOTIVATION IN THE WORKS OF EASTERN SCIENTISTS

Yuldashova Dilafruz Shavkatovna

Teacher of the Department of Psychology of Tashkent state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8048148>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the decline of educational motivation, the factors influencing the formation of educational motivation, especially the role of the family environment, based on the research results of Eastern scientists.*

Keywords: *motive, motivation, educational motivation, interpersonal relations, factors that develop motivation, family environment.*

In the works of great scholars, the acquisition of knowledge is given a lot of space, and it is clear that, both in the past and now, where the attention to the field of education is high, there the progress has always advanced.

In the works of encyclopedic scientists of the East, along with their thoughts on education and personal development, a number of scientific information is presented on the ways of acquiring knowledge. For example, such scholars as Imam al-Bukhari, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Burkhaniddin Zarnuji, Mahmud Koshgari, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Omar Khayyam, Abu Hamid Bazzoli, Alisher Nawai, Muhammad Reza Ogahi, Abdullah Awlani and the works of thinkers provide detailed information.

The encyclopedist Imam al-Bukhari also placed the study of knowledge on a high level, and in his works, a person is a mature muhaddith until he receives hadith not only from those who are superior to him or his peers, but also from those who are inferior to him. emphasizing that it cannot be, with this opinion, he emphasizes that the positive motives of educational activity are formed by the teacher-teacher.

Abu Nasr Farabi pays great attention to the issue of knowledge in many of his works. He distinguishes two levels of knowledge - emotional and intellectual knowledge and recognizes the high importance of human intelligence in knowledge. Farabi called people to be knowledgeable and put forward exemplary ideas about the role of the student in social life and its unique characteristics. He emphasizes that only if the teacher works tirelessly to educate the student and make him knowledgeable, the student can strive to study, learn, and become educated. When a pedagogue says that he will give knowledge to a student, he must be truthful in front of the student, he must be dignified, he must value his honor, he must be fair to his students, he must be determined to achieve his goal. It is permissible to be able to show and be an example, says the thinker. Farabi prefers understanding, reading and understanding the essence of knowledge over mere memorization. According to scolar, any student should be aware of his own behavior, i.e. self-awareness, according to the terminology of modern psychology, should have the skills of self-reflection and one who can achieve happiness through these efforts should understand his humanity. Farabi is a scientist who objectively commented on a number of qualities characteristic of a student's personality.

According to the encyclopedist Abu Ali ibn Sina, human thinking and the power of the mind consist of several stages. At first, the mental forces are absolutely calm and quiet. An example of this is the mental strength of children in learning to read and write. Abu Ali ibn Sina

called these forces material forces, that is, these forces can be understood as external motives. Gradually, these forces turn into action, they are the result of the tool of labor, that is, they come into action and are manifested through the tool of labor. This situation can be explained by the fact that the child wants to write, but does not have a pen as a writing instrument. Ibn Sina called these two powers the power that can be realized. Finally, the third force is explained by the lack of will. That is, such a situation has power, but the child lacks the will to use it and realize it. In his view, intelligence and knowledge acquisition are explained by these three conditions.

In the short story “Hayy ibn Yakzon”, where Ibn Sina calls to study the science of logic in order to understand human character and psyche. This science greatly contributes to the expansion of the scope of human thinking. To know the nature of people, you need to read, and to be aware of the science of clairvoyance to sharpen your mind. Al-Farabi encouraged to learn science through musical and philosophical knowledge, while Ibn Sina encouraged through the science of logic.

Abu Ali ibn Sina was one of the supporters of taking responsibility for children's education. He says that when the child reaches the age of 6, he will be handed over to the teacher for education. Even now, the fact that children are admitted to primary classes from the age of 7 shows how important Ibn Sina's ideas are at that time. In his opinion, it is permissible to teach a child gradually. Allama says that it should not be tied to a book at once. Ibn Sina emphasizes that people should be educated carefully so that they are able to live and do not suffer for nothing, that is, he encourages them not to extinguish their positive motivation to study, and that the role of the pedagogue is great in this regard. emphasizes separately.

Thoughts on the students' reading activities are also reflected in the works of the encyclopedist Abu Raikhan Beruni. According to him, in order to get knowledge, students must first have aspiration and interest. In fact, if a person does not have the desire, effort and interest to learn and research something, he cannot achieve anything. One of the important ways to acquire knowledge is that a person should be friendly to everyone and be able to do good to other people. From the point of view of modern psychology, these opinions of the scientist can be interpreted as educational motives can be formed only if there is a need for educational activities.

Beruni says that those who prioritize moral purity in learning and conduct education and upbringing in the same consistency will reach the level of a perfect human being. Beruni emphasizes that a teacher should constantly improve his skills and knowledge and adapt to the times. He pays special attention to the methods of reading books. It gives information about the need to read books in small sections and summarize them. Beruni emphasizes that it is necessary to work not only by inductive (general conclusion), but also by deductive (partial conclusion) way in teaching, thinking expands and knowledge increases in this kind of study.

Abu Raykhan Beruni emphasizes the need to focus the student's attention on thinking operations such as comparison and comparison. Even today, conscious, expressive, correct and fast reading is a process related to thinking and is one of the main components that ensure the literacy of modern students.

Abu Raykhan Beruni is a great person who promoted the use of various psychological methods, thereby enriching their thinking and deepening their knowledge, without forcing repetition and boring young students. He admits that in order not to extinguish children's interest in reading, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of their age.

Using the ideas of Abu Raykhan Beruni about generating interest in reading through thinking operations such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalization as a

methodological basis in our research, we paid attention to the formation of these thinking operations in formative experience.

Another great scientist of the East, Burkhaniddin Zarnuji, in his book “A guide to the student’s education” says: “The best time to learn is when you are young, early in the morning and when the sun is dark. Let the learner get used to organizing this time effectively, and if one subject is boring for him, let him be busy with another”. In his book “Ta’limul – mutaallim” he recognizes the principle of unity of education.

Mahmud Koshgari, who lived and created in the 11th century, also called for learning in his work “Devonu Lugatit Turk”. In the work “O my son, learn from me, take advice, try to be polite and well-educated, so that you will be known as a scholar in the country and spread manners and knowledge among them”, Learn knowledge, wisdom, “Don’t be arrogant in learning, a person who brags about being knowledgeable without learning anything will be ashamed and pitied during the exam” is a vivid example of this.

Yusuf Khos Khajib, one of the great thinkers of Central Asia, also highly values knowledge in his work. He compares knowledge to things like wealth, clothes, and food. He writes about the need to be able to feel knowledge and knowledge, to understand it, being knowledgeable is closely related to education, and the earlier a child is educated, the more eager he is to learn.

Reflections on the psychological characteristics and personal qualities of the reader are deeply covered in the works of the encyclopedist Omar Khayyam. According to Omar Khayyam, students are not limited to the knowledge they get from the teacher, they acquire knowledge, skills and skills in the process of learning and observing the events in life, and repeating them many times in various ways during practice. that is, the scientist puts forward the principle of an integral relationship between the subject of education and life. In his opinion, it is necessary to form independent thinking in students, while organically connecting learning and education with practice.

Abu Hamid Bazzoli’s thoughts about the unity of science and practice in human life are also worthy of attention. He said that a person should apply the acquired theoretical knowledge in practice, because not only knowledge and science, but also the ability to apply the achievements of science and experience in practice is one of the human qualities.

Alisher Navoi, a great thinker and scholar, highly valued human thinking, intellect and knowledge. He writes, “Knowledge and wisdom are the adornment of a person”. Alisher Navoi says that children should be given knowledge, information and education from a young age, and like Ibn Sina, they should be given to a teacher from the age of 6.

The talented poet, translator, and historian Muhammed Reza Ogakhi mentions in his works that in order for a person to reach full maturity, it is necessary to acquire knowledge and skills from a young age. In his opinion, knowledge is a powerful tool for the spiritual maturity of a person and the development of society. Science enriches the human mind. Ogahiy tries to deliver knowledge through folk games, because these games serve to form a positive learning motive. Folk games are actually psychological games. At this time, the child learns and develops.

One of the scientists who played a leading role in the development of pedagogical ideas in the socio-political life of Uzbekistan at the beginning of the 20th century is Abdulla Avloni. According to his opinion, science is the destiny, life, leader, and blessing of people. In order to learn, to become a scientist, it is necessary to go to school and learn from a teacher.

He not only shows the theoretical importance of science, but also emphasizes that it is a vital necessity for practical activity. It is emphasized that science saves us from the darkness of ignorance, brings us to the world of culture and enlightenment, turns us away from bad deeds and bad deeds, and makes us possess good manners and manners. At the same time, he repeats again and again that our whole life, health, happiness, pleasure, enthusiasm, world and hereafter depend on science.

Science sharpens a person's mind and thoughts like a sword. A person without knowledge is like a tree without fruit. Science, like the fruits of a tree, gives food to every person and leads to the world of culture, spirituality and enlightenment. Prevents bad people and bad deeds. It serves to be well-behaved and polite. As a result, people of knowledge will be dear and respected everywhere. Science is the tool that guides a person's life in a real and correct way. That is why great people who have acquired high qualities through knowledge and achieved greatness and dreams are highly valued among the people.

Knowledge is the best of professions and virtues. Through science, a person can know good and bad, distinguish between good and bad, understand the qualities of friendship and kinship, and know his rights.

It is impossible to imagine the development of society without the development of people's knowledge, science, and practical skills. People who do not have certain spiritual needs and high moral qualities do not have the desire to study science, work honestly, acquire a profession, and improve their qualifications. Therefore, at all stages of the development of the society, they first brought up young people and then gave them education.

Indeed, the need for knowledge is a system of conscious motives. A person determines the possibilities of solving a problem with his intelligence, knowledge, strength and will. Knowledge is broader in terms of content and includes all concepts, ideas, and practical skills acquired by a person through life experience. Science is the pinnacle of knowledge. Knowledge becomes science only as a result of in-depth study of the laws of nature, society, human psyche.

In conclusion, we can say that Eastern scholars tried to analyze educational motives from the point of view of needs. The formation of these needs and their development can be achieved mainly by taking into account the psychological characteristics of the educational process by professors, that is, by taking into account the physiological and psychological characteristics of students during the study process, by approaching them as individually as possible. confessed. In the works of Eastern thinkers, the great treasure, which is a great treasure for science, advanced ideas related to education and upbringing of students have not lost their importance to this day.

REFERENCES

1. Abu Nasr Farobiy. Fozil odamlar shahri.—Toshkent: A.Qodiriy nomidagi nashriyot, 1993. 224.
2. Asomova R.Z. Kasb tanlash motivatsiyasi va uning dinamikasi: psixologiya fanlari nomzodi ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. - Toshkent: UzMU 2002,- 137 b.
3. Pedagogika tarixi: K.Xoshimov, S.Nishonova, M.Inomova va bop. - Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1996.- 48 b.
4. Давлетшин М.Г. Танланган илмий ишлар тўплами.—Тошкент: ТДПУ, 2008, 81б.
5. Газиев Э.Г. Психологические основы развития самоуправления учебной деятельностью у школьников и студентов: Автореф. дис... докт. психол. наук. – М.: МГУ, 1992. – 38 с.